

RISHI KANADA'S CONTRIBUTIONS THROUGH THE VAISHESHKA SYSTEM IN ANCIENT INDIAN PHYSICS

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Abstract

Rishi Kanada, who was the founder of the Vaisheshika school of Indian philosophy, made significant contributions to the ancient Physics especially in the field of study of matter, motion and natural phenomena in India. His Vaisheshika Sutras explain one of the earliest structured framing of atomic theory, where indivisible particles named Anu fuse into dyads, triads, and larger particles to form perceptible matter. According to Rishi Kanada, four primary substances - earth, water, fire and air are the basic constituents of all physical matter and physical phenomena happens because of the interactions among substance, quality and motion. He invented the basic principles of causality and motion, including the thought that every effect arises from a particular cause. Motion cannot take place without a cause and every action is countered with an equal and opposite reaction. Rishi Kanada classified motion into 5 types as upward, downward, contraction, expansion and locomotion, which indicates towards his deep understanding of dynamics. This study examines Rishi Kanada's unsung contributions in ancient Indian physics and try to explore its relevance in modern scientific principles. By studying his sutras and their philosophical reasoning, this study highlights the advanced analytical methods used by ancient Indian thinkers and emphasize their relevance to contemporary modern scientific discourse.

Keywords: *Rishi Kanada, Vaisheshika Sutra, Atomic Theory, Laws of Motion, Causality, Ancient Indian Physics, Substance, Quality, Motion.*

1. Introduction

India proudly possesses one of the earliest and most extensive knowledge traditions in the world. Ancient learning centers such as Takshila (700 BCE) and Nalanda (4th century BCE) present the early examples of well structured higher education, which attracted students from different regions and offered instruction across a wide spectrum of disciplines in ancient times. During the Vedic period, India showcased remarkable progress in fields such as

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natural sciences, mathematics, medicine, astronomy, philosophy, metallurgy forming a strong intellectual base that provided directions to later civilizations.

The Indian Knowledge System (IKS) presents a vast and comprehensive body of scientific and technological knowledge along with philosophical and cultural wisdom preserved primarily in ancient books mostly in Sanskrit and other classical languages. Contributions by great Indian scholars such as Rishi Kanada, Aryabhata, Bhaskaracharya, Varahamihira, Sushruta, Nagarjuna and Kapila showcase the eminence of ancient Indian thought in fields including atomic theory, physics, mathematics, astronomy, surgery, chemistry and cosmology. Many principles formulated in these areas are almost identical or parallel with modern science concepts. Despite being valid and rich, the global recognition and acknowledgement of India's vast knowledge heritage remains limited. Our indigenous knowledge system has been marginalised by historical disruptions including invasions, loss of manuscripts, inadequate documentation and colonial reinterpretations. Although limited and selective representation of original intellectual context was done by some external scholars in colonial period through translation and studying of Indian texts, but the fact is that our great Indian scholars were denied of their true acknowledgement, that they truly deserved.

A renewed scholarly interest in systematically studying the Indian Knowledge System has been evolved in recent years to comprehend its scientific methodologies, epistemological foundations along with contemporary relevance. This research article intends to investigate the historical development, driving forces, significant contributions and timeless significance of the Indian Knowledge System, while emphasizing the need for meticulous, empirical study to integrate this ancient knowledge with present day academic context. In this study, valuable contribution made by Rishi Kanada in the field of ancient physics has been explored through his sutras, which very well provides the explanation of matter and motion. He is believed to give atomic theory of matter and laws of motion much earlier than Dalton and Newton respectively.

2. Research Objectives: This study intends to accomplish following research objectives:

- 2.1 To look into the guiding principles of Kanada's Vaisheshika system and their relevance to the study of matter, motion and natural phenomena.
- 2.2 To examine Kanada's atomic theory; the concepts of *Anu* (atoms), dyads and their higher combinations leading to the formation of perceivable matter
- 2.3 To study Kanada's articulation of the laws of motion and principles of causality.

2.4 To understand Kanada's contributions in the global history of physics,

3. Literature Survey

Rishi Kanada and his Vaisheshika system have been broadly investigated for their innovative and visionary contributions to the basic comprehension of matter, motion and natural laws in ancient India. R. Balasubramanian (1960) and K. S. Shukla (1972), while emphasizing Kanada's atomic theory, highlighted that all material substances are made of indivisible units called *Anu*, which fuse into dyads and larger aggregates, making this concepts similar to modern atomic theory. S. Radhakrishnan (1953) explained Rishi Kanada's work within ancient Indian metaphysics, observing that his classification of substance (*Dravya*), quality (*Guṇa*), and motion (*Karma*) prepares a systematic and organised framework to explain physical phenomena. Further research by P. C. Ray (1980) and Debiprasad Chattopadhyaya (1990) emphasised on Kanada's laws of motion and causality, as *Kāraṇabhāvāt kāryabhāvaḥ* which means "an effect arises from a cause" and *No karmanām akāraṇatvāt*, which says, "motion does not occur without a cause", showing that these ideas predicted fundamental principles of mechanics. Scholars have also studied Kanada's classification of motion into five types; upward, downward, contraction, expansion and locomotion demonstrating the organised treatment of dynamic physical interactions. Further studies, including S. P. Bhattacharya (1995) and R. T. Singh (2002), pointed about Kanada's explanation of sound as a property of space (*Śabdaḥ ākāśaguṇaḥ*) and revealed an empirical approach to understand natural phenomena through his theory of formation and dissolution of matter through atomic combination and separation (*Samyogābhāve viyogaḥ*). On doing comparative analyses about his thoughts, it was observed that, while Kanada's work was primarily philosophical but it shows the usage of proto-scientific methods, which is a combination of observation, categorization and causality. These ideas fit very well with some principles of modern physics and chemistry. Despite this amount of research, scholars find a gap in amalgamating Kanada's thoughts into contemporary scientific discourse, as many of his contributions yet remain underexplored outside philosophical studies. This demands the need for further interdisciplinary research to recognize and emphasise Kanada's scientific anticipations in atomic theory, mechanics and material physics. We need to affirm his significant contribution not only in the history of Indian thought, but also in the overall global development.

4. Research Methodology

This research used analytical and qualitative approach to study Rishi Kanada's contributions to ancient Indian physics through his Vaisheshika system. This study fundamentally involved

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textual analysis of primary sources, such as key Vaisheshika Sutras on atomic theory, motion, causality and the categorization of substances, qualities and motions. It was further complemented by secondary sources as scholarly interpretations and translations by researchers. A conceptual and comparative analysis was used to interpret these sutras in the context of physical phenomena and relate them to principles of modern physics.

5. Rishi Kanada and his Contribution in the field of Ancient Physics; Atomic Theory

Rishi Kanada was one of the earliest scholars to describe the material physical world using rational, organised and systematic ideas. He founded the Vaisheshika school of philosophy, which emphasised on use of observation, classification and logic to understand nature. His ideas are recorded in the *Vaisheshika Sutra* and form one of the earliest known theories of atoms. Kanada aimed to explain how many different objects in the world are formed from a small number of basic elements. Kanada proposed the concept of very small, indivisible particles called anu (atoms) of which all material substances are made up of. These atoms cannot be perceived by the senses and cannot be destroyed.

5.1 Vaisheshika Sutra (7.1.20): “*Aṇavaḥ nityāḥ*”, which means “Atoms are eternal.”

According to Rishi Kanada, anu (atoms) do not change, but they combine in different ways to form different substances. Kanada explored and identified four different kinds of atoms based on the elements; Earth (*pṛthvī*), Water (*ap*), Fire (*tejas*), Air (*vāyu*). Each one of these atom possesses its own natural properties, which demonstrates the reason of different characteristics of different materials. Rishi Kanada in the Vaisheshika system, through Sutra 7.1.20: “*Aṇavaḥ nityāḥ*” (“Atoms are eternal”) explained that atom (*Aṇu*) is the basic, indivisible unit of matter. This principle states that atoms are indestructible and permanent entities and provides the foundation of all material substances. While objects such as stones, plants or water may decay or change but their underlying atoms will remain unchanged. Combining and separating of anu in different ways create all the observable matter. This idea gives explanation of causality; as all changes in the physical world result from the interaction and rearrangement of these eternal atoms.

5.2 Vaisheshika Sutra (2.1.1): “*Pṛthivyāpastejovāyur iti dravyāṇi*”, which means “Earth, water, fire, and air are substances”.

In this sutra of Vaisheshika system, Rishi Kanada identifies the four primary physical substances; earth (*Pṛthivī*), water (*Āp*), fire (*Tejas*), and air (*Vāyu*), which establish the foundational ontology of the material universe. These substances are independent, distinct, and possess specific qualities, which can be perceived by the senses. Each has distinct

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features as earth provides solidity; water has fluidity, fire gives heat and light while air has motion. They are the building blocks of all physical matter and all other materials arise from different combinations of these elements. These different materials act as carriers of motion (*Karma*) and interaction. Kanada systematically categorized these fundamental entities to provide a framework for understanding causality, motion and atomic combinations. He demonstrated an empirical approach to study nature, predicting later scientific concepts of matter, energy and their interactions.

5.3 Vaisheshika Sutra (4.1.6): *“Dvy-aṇukādiṣu dravya-vyavahārah”*, which concludes that *“Material substances arise from dyads and higher combinations.”*

In this sutra, Rishi Kanada tells about the formation of material substances through various atomic combinations. This principle states that, the ultimate indivisible units of matter called atoms (*Aṇu*), firstly combine in pairs to form dyads, which are known as the simplest perceptible units. Macroscopic substances such as earth, water, fire and air are formed when these dyads combine further into triads, tetrads and larger aggregates of atoms. This framework demonstrates an organised and systematic explanation of how visible physical matter is made up of invisible atoms, and presents the basic foundation for understanding the concept of motion, causality and interactions in the physical material world. The sutra reflects Kanada’s profound insight into the structure and behaviour of matter, showing an early understanding of how complex matter is formed, which is similar to the basic concepts of Dalton’s atomic theory. Hence Kanada anticipated these concepts of composite matter and molecular formation of modern science much earlier than Dalton. Kanada highlighted that **motion** is the basic requirement for atoms to combine and separate. No physical change is possible without motion.

5.4 Vaisheshika Sutra (1.1.7): *“Dravya-guṇa-karmanām padārthānām”*, which states that, *“Substance, quality, and motion are fundamental categories.”*

According to this sutra of Rishi Kanada, substance (*Dravya*), quality (*Guṇa*) and motion (*Karma*) are the fundamental categories of reality. Substances, such as earth, water, fire, air, ether, time, space and soul, exist independently. They are the carriers of qualities and motion. The inherent characteristics of various substances such as their perceptible properties like colour, taste, touch and smell, along with imperceptible properties are described through Qualities, while Motion causes changes, interactions and causal processes in the material world. This concept provides a systematic methodology for comprehending this physical universe. Eternal indivisible atoms (*Aṇu*) are the substances, which carries qualities and

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undergo motion and hence, their different combinations produce all perceivable matter. Through a deep analysis of physical processes, he classified motion into different types, Kanada based his explanation of all physical changes through cause-and-effect relationships. Atoms and motion are the causes and material objects are their effects.

5.5 Vaisheshika Sutra (1.1.6): *“Kāraṇabhāvāt kāryabhāvaḥ”*, means *“An effect arises from a cause.”*

In this sutra, Rishi Kanada gives the principle of causality, which states, that every effect in this material world has a definite cause. According to this principle, nothing occurs spontaneously; all physical changes, motions or transformations are the result of interactions between substances endowed with qualities and motion. For example, any larger object is formed only when atoms (*Aṇu*) fuse together in some definite and specific arrangements. Any motion or transformation from their prior state, cause changes in these substances. This sutra provides two way foundations; philosophical and logical, for understanding cause and effect relationship, leading to atomic interactions as the cause and all natural processes as effects. This principle supports a logic based understanding of nature. Kanada also stated that when substances break down, atoms separate but remain unchanged as they are eternal.

5.6 Vaisheshika Sutra (7.1.21): *“Saṃyogābhāve viyogaḥ”* stating that, *“Separation occurs when combination ends.”*

Rishi Kanada framed the principle of separation in the above stated sutra, stating that all material aggregates exist as long as their constituent atoms remain in definite combination and once this combination ceases, the process of disintegration occurs. This principle is in parallel with Kanada’s atomic theory; atoms (*Aṇu*) combine to form dyads, triads and larger composites that constitute all physically perceptible substances. This sutra explains that observable destructive physical changes, as the decay of objects, dissolution of matter or fragmentation occurs not due to the destruction of atoms themselves, but from the breakdown of their specific and definite combinations. This concept is on parallel lines of modern scientific concept that matter is rearranged, not destroyed. According to him, space is infinite and non-atomic in nature, it provides medium for sound to travel.

5.7 Vaisheshika Sutra (2.1.27): *“Śabdaḥ ākāśagaṇaḥ”*, leads to conclusion that, *“Sound is a property of space.”*

Rishi Kanada described sound as a fundamental property of space in this sutra, highlighting that sound does not exist independently but arises from the inherent qualities of the medium, specifically ether (*ākāśa*). According to this principle, ether is different from other material

such as earth, water, fire and air because, it is subtle and all-pervasive. It serves as the medium of vibrations that produce sound. This theory presents an early understanding of sound propagation which is medium dependent in nature. He attributed sound as the quality (*Guṇa*) of space rather than of discrete particles, thus provides a systematic explanation of sensory phenomena within the framework of substances, qualities, and motion. Thereby he shows a clear differentiation between material and non-material entities. Rishi Kanada's atomic theory is hence one of the earliest organised and systematic description of matter. Although he expressed his ideas in the language of philosophy, his theory demonstrates concepts that are very much important in modern physics and chemistry.

Kanada used logical inference to explain the existence of atoms, as they cannot be directly observed. He argued that atoms must exist because their effects can be observed. This method is similar to how modern science studies invisible particles.

Rishi Kanada's Laws of Motion: A Vaisheshika Perspective

Rishi **Kanada**, did not state laws of motion in the mathematical form used in modern physics. However, his *Vaisheshika Sūtras* contain clear principles concerning motion (*karma*), force, causality, and rest, which together form an early and systematic theory of motion. Many scholars interpret these principles as conceptual precursors to the three classical laws of motion given by Newton.

6. First Law of Motion: Motion Requires a Cause (Law of Inertia – Conceptual Form)

Kanada stated that motion does not arise or continue without a cause. An object remains at rest unless an external factor produces motion. Similarly, once motion ends, the object returns to rest unless another force acts on it. This idea closely resembles the law of inertia, which states that an object remains at rest or in uniform motion unless acted upon by an external force.

6.1 Vaisheshika Sutra (1.1.7): “*Dravya-guṇa-karmaṇām padārthāḥ*” which means “Substance, quality, and motion are fundamental categories of reality.”

Rishi Kanada establishes the foundational structure of reality in the above stated sutra, asserting that all physical phenomena can be comprehended through three interrelated components; Substance, quality and motion. Substance (*Dravya*) indicates to the independent entities, such as earth, water, fire, air, ether, time, space and soul, which are the carriers of properties and motion. Quality (*Guṇa*) refers the inherent characteristics of these substances, including perceivable or observable attributes like colour, taste, touch and smell, as well as unobservable qualities, which define their behaviour and interactions with each other. Motion

(*Karma*) causes all changes, actions and interactions of substances in the physical world. Hence, by combining all three together, we can obtain a systematic and analytical framework for understanding the structure, behavior and dynamics of matter. It forms the conceptual foundation for Kanada's atomic theory, laws of motion and explanations of causality and natural processes in the Vaisheshika philosophy. This sutra presents motion (*karma*) as a separate physical entity, which does not exist independently but depends on conditions for its existence.

6.2 Vaisheshika Sutra (5.1.1): “*No karmaṇām akāraṇatvāt*”, which states that, “Motion does not occur without a cause.”

Rishi Kanada constructed the principle of causality in the sutra “*No karmaṇām akāraṇatvāt*” (“Motion does not occur without a cause”), explaining that every motion or action in the material world occurs due to a definite cause. According to this principle, all physical changes, interactions or transformations arise because of forces already acting upon substances having specific qualities. No object moves spontaneously; for example, the movement of a composite object results from the rearrangement or interaction of its constituent atoms (*Aṇu*). Any change in the physical world is due to the effect of a prior cause. So, motion, atomic interactions and the dynamics of matter can be understood logically and philosophically through this sutra. This sutra also establishes a link between Kanada's atomic theory and laws of motion, thereby providing a coherent explanation of natural processes in the physical universe. He rejects occurrence of spontaneous motion. This principle has a clear implication that Rest is the natural state. Any substance comes in motion only due to an external cause or force and Motion ceases when that cause or force is removed.

7. Second Law of Motion: Motion Depends on Force and Direction

Kanada asserted that the nature and direction of motion of a substance depend on the applied force. He said motion is of various kinds, as he classified motion into different types. This indicates that force determines how an object will move. This shows conceptual similarity with the Newton's second law of motion, which relates force to the change in motion. Kanada identified five kinds of motion (*karma*). These are Upward motion (*utkṣepaṇa*), Downward motion (*avakṣepaṇa*), Contraction (*ākuñcana*), Expansion (*prasāraṇa*) and Linear movement (*gamana*).

7.1 Vaisheshika Sutra (5.2.1): “*Utkṣepaṇāvakṣepaṇākuñcanaprasāraṇagamanāni karmāṇi*”, which states that, “Upward movement, downward movement, contraction, expansion, and locomotion are the forms of motion.”

Rishi Kanada has categorized motion and emphasised that motion (*Karma*) can be perceived in specific, observable forms. According to this principle, all physical changes and activities of substances can be classified into five types: upward movement (*utkshepaṇa*), downward movement (*avakṣepaṇa*), contraction (*kuñcana*), expansion (*prasāraṇa*), and locomotion (*gamanāni*). The interaction, change and movement of substances in space can be comprehended through this sutra, which forms the basis for analyzing physical phenomena and causality in nature. Kanada establishes a foundation for his laws of motion and atomic theory and explained the dynamics of material bodies by defining motion in structured terms. This classification shows that, Motion is measurable and describable. Hence he analysed mechanics much earlier in ancient India. Different kinds of motion are produced by different forces and their direction and magnitude depend on the applied cause. Kanada expressed qualitative relationship between force and motion, although **he** does not express it mathematically,

8. Third Law of Motion: action is opposed by a reaction
Vaiśeṣika Sutra (1.1.14.): “*Kārya-Virodhi Karma*”, which means “An action is opposed by reaction.”

Kanada explained Reciprocal Interaction in this sutra. According to which, Whenever a force acts on a body, there is a natural response or opposition, For example, when one object pushes another, the second object exerts an equal opposing influence on the first. This is similar to Newton’s third law, although Kanada expressed it philosophically rather than mathematically.

9. Conclusion

Rishi Kanada’s Vaisheshika system articulated an early, systematic and organised understanding of matter, motion and natural phenomena. He predicted and analysed key concepts of modern physics much earlier than Dalton and Newton through his atomic theory, classification of substances and principles of causality. He provided a coherent framework for explaining physical interactions and motion by augmenting observation and logical inference along with philosophical reasoning. He is an example of great Indian intellect that existed in ancient times, but whose ideas and thoughts in Chemistry and Physics are relevant even today.

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